

Interview Script

Research objectives: We aim to obtain the interviewees' perceptions, based on their professional experience, about what a company should do to change from an independent software product approach to a software ecosystem.

Profile of the Participants

- (1) What information should be understood about customers, in addition to their needs (requirements)?
- (2) How to obtain partners with the desired profile?
- (3) How can the company expand the portfolio of partners to enable the expansion of the software ecosystem to different niche markets?

Platform Quality

- (4) How to enable the integration of partner solutions with the ecosystem software platform?
- (5) What strategies can the company and its partners adopt to evolve the ecosystem software platform?
- (6) What strategies can be adopted to ensure that the company's partners maintain an adequate quality of products?

Attraction and Maintenance of Participants

- (7) What strategies can be used to create a number of solutions sufficient to launch the ecosystem platform on the market?
- (8) How should the monetization policy be defined in the software ecosystem?
- (9) What actions can be used to stimulate the attraction of new partners?
- (10) What actions can be used to stimulate the attraction of new customers?
- (11) How to avoid the participation of customers in the company's ecosystem and the ecosystem of competitors simultaneously?

Support for the Partner

- (12) In your opinion, what are the appropriate strategies to support partners in obtaining new customers and markets?
- (13) What actions can the company take to help partners develop the necessary skills to provide complementary solutions to the ecosystem platform?
- (14) How to promote effective communication with partners?